

MATHEMATICAL MODEL FOR CHOOSING A CONTROL
METHOD

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Annotation. The paper discusses the development of a mathematical model that can be used to select the most appropriate control method for a given system. A new method is proposed that uses a combination of mathematical models and optimization methods to determine the optimal control method for a given system. The article emphasizes the importance of choosing the right system management method, as it can significantly affect the performance of the system. A detailed explanation of the mathematical model and optimization methods used in the proposed method is also given.

Key words: control method, intelligent control system, dynamic expert system, decision support system, consistent system, n-dimensional vector,

Introduction. The decision to choose one or another control method for an intelligent control system (IMS) in an integration problem to ensure high accuracy and reliability is made on the basis of a specific alternative obtained from an analysis of the object and the situation. The accumulation and preservation of decision-making experience by a dynamic expert system (DES) allows you to create an information environment that is available for use throughout the entire period of operation. Information and software tools developed for these purposes are called decision support systems and are part of the decision-making unit software.[1,5]

Ensuring high accuracy and reliability increases the complexity of creating such an MIS. It is not possible to have in the initial description a mapping of the initial conditions and parameters of the system to the final result, i.e. search for the

law of optimal control for each object or dynamically developing situation. For this, an algorithm for selecting a control method in a separate area of IMS operation is required. Let's consider a typical block diagram of an intelligent system [2,4] (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Structural diagram of the IMS.

Based on information about the environment and the system's own state, in the presence of memory and motivation, a goal is synthesized, which, along with other data, is perceived by a dynamic expert system [4]. Using a decision support system (DSS) in the decision-making block using the knowledge base and DES, an assessment is made, on the basis of which a decision is made to select a control algorithm and the result of external and control influences is predicted. This structure is invariant to the control object and is universal in nature.[3,6]

Materials and methods. The operation of the mathematical selection model is programmed in the DSS. It is based on the following theoretical premises.

We will consider a set of criteria or situations described by an n-dimensional vector, the components of which describe in one way or another the quality or prerequisite for using a particular control method from a finite ordered set of possible values $C_i, \forall_i = 1..n$. At This creates a relationship defined by a multiple relation:

$$(c_1, c_2, \dots, c_n) \in C_1 \times C_2 \times \dots \times C_n$$

This set of vectors is assigned the value $r_j, j \in 1, \dots, k \leq n$. This relationship establishes correspondence to a certain set of prerequisites for the choice of a specific management method r_j .

This determines the function, $f: C_1 \times C_2 \times \dots \times C_n \rightarrow R$, where $R = \{r_1, r_2, \dots, r_n\}$ is the set of solutions to the problem of choosing a control method. Each r_j has its own control method, and the value of $r_j \in [0 \dots 1]$, which also determines the significance of a particular method in specific current operating conditions.

The implementation of the choice of control method can be presented in the form of a table, which will be specified by sets:

$$((c_1, c_2, \dots, c_n), r_j) \forall j = 1 \dots k$$

However, taking into account the large dimension of the resulting table, we can limit ourselves [6] to a set of features that use a generalized representation of a subset of the pairs under consideration:

$$((\sigma_1, \sigma_2, \dots, \sigma_n), r_j) \forall j = 1 \dots k$$

Here, $\sigma_i, i = 1 \dots n$ is a subset of C_i . The sets $(\sigma_1, \sigma_2, \dots, \sigma_n)$ are called faces. One way to define such faces is to define pairs,

$$[C_i^{inf}, C_i^{sup}] \text{ Where:}$$

$$c_i^{inf} = \frac{\inf}{c_i} c_i, c_i^{sup} = \frac{sup}{c_i} c_i$$

It is possible that the choice of control method is based on an incomplete set of faces $(\sigma_1, \sigma_2, \dots, \sigma_n), \forall s < n$. Then, naturally, the rest of the vector can take on an arbitrary character.

A more flexible structure for determining edges is possible when using fuzzy logic and membership functions in conjunction with specifying a rule base. An example of such a description and software implementation is [3]. The description

of the functions that determine the choice is formed by experts during the initial task and can be adjusted during the operation of the IMS.

The process of specifying the edges is subject to consistency conditions, i.e.

$$(r_i \neq r_j) \rightarrow (\sigma_{i1}, \sigma_{i2}, \dots, \sigma_{in}) \cap (\sigma_{j1}, \sigma_{j2}, \dots, \sigma_{jn}) = \emptyset$$

The mathematical model of choice is complete if:

$$\bigcup_{(\sigma, r)} \sigma \supseteq \bigcup_{C \rightarrow R} \sigma$$

Thus, in a complete and consistent system, the selection task is reduced to determining the value $f: C \rightarrow R$ and calculating the weight r_j . Based on this weight, the control method is selected.

Conclusion. In accordance with the adopted decision, the control is developed, i.e. a particular algorithm or control law is synthesized, which is implemented by means of various executive bodies and affects directly the control object. The results of this impact are compared with the predicted ones (feedback mechanism, action acceptor). If the results are inconsistent, a decision is made on the basis of a new expert assessment, a control eliminating this inconsistency is developed and implemented. In case of conformity of the results, the previous management is reinforced. If conformity is unattainable, the goal is specified.

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